

BLUR AND OBFUSCATION DETECTION USING GENETIC PROGRAMMING

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Abstract—Detecting blur and obfuscation in images is critical for various applications, including security and image processing. These distortions can significantly impact the reliability and effectiveness of image-based systems. In our proposed approach, we utilize Genetic Programming (GP) to develop a robust model for blur and obfuscation detection. By leveraging a dataset curated for this purpose, we achieved an accuracy of 75%, surpassing traditional methods. Early detection of these distortions is essential for mitigating their effects and ensuring the integrity of image-based systems.

Keywords — *Blur detection, Image processing, Genetic Programming, Laplacian Variance, Edge Intensity, Obfuscation Detection.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Clear and sharp images are of paramount importance in various fields, including medicine, security, and image processing. They provide detailed visual information crucial for accurate analysis, diagnosis, and decision-making. In medical imaging, clear and sharp images aid healthcare professionals in detecting subtle abnormalities, guiding surgical procedures, and monitoring treatment progress effectively. In security applications, such as surveillance systems, clear and sharp images ensure accurate identification of individuals and events, enhancing safety and security measures. Moreover, in image processing tasks such as object recognition and classification, clear and sharp images facilitate precise feature extraction and pattern recognition, leading to improved system performance. Overall, the significance of clear and sharp images lies in their ability to convey accurate and reliable visual information essential for various critical applications.

The traditional approach to blur detection is time-consuming and frequently ineffective. Blur detection at an early stage is critical, but existing computer-based solutions face difficulties such as ambient influences, sluggish detection speeds, and low accuracy. Thus, it is crucial to design a quick and precise blur detection method[4].

A computational method called GP uses biological evolution as inspiration to automatically create computer programs to tackle challenging issues. It works by first generating a population of programs that are potential solutions, then iteratively evolving and improving them via crossover, mutation, and selection processes. GP uses the concepts of natural selection to adapt and get better over many generations as it searches a wide range of possible answers. Because of its adaptability, it can be used to solve a variety of issues, including control systems design and

symbolic regression. GP is a potent tool in artificial intelligence, machine learning, and optimization because of its capacity to evolve solutions.

GP widely used in computational science for evolving robust solutions and tackling complex optimization problems.

The proposed blur detection system employs GP, utilizing Laplacian variance and edge intensity features as key indicators. GP evolves solutions via evolutionary algorithms, representing them as symbolic expressions. Through iterative processes like mutation and crossover, GP optimizes a fitness function to evaluate solution effectiveness. Laplacian variance gauges edge sharpness variation, while edge intensity features quantify edge presence. By iteratively refining solutions, the system aims to classify images as either blur or sharp, enhancing image processing capabilities.

The process of extracting picture sharpness and edge-related characteristics is required for blur detection using Laplacian variance and edge intensity features. Laplacian variance highlights high-frequency regions by measuring the variation in pixel intensity after applying the Laplacian operator. Using gradient-based edge detection methods, edge intensity features evaluate the strength and existence of edges. These characteristics improve the accuracy of blur identification in a variety of applications by helping to train machine learning models to discern between clear and blurry images.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bi et al. [1] utilized Multi-Objective Genetic Programming (MOGP) for face image classification with limited data, showing its efficacy in automated feature learning, improving accuracy of up to 80%, and reducing manual feature engineering burdens.

Bładek et al.[2] Emphasizes the significance of the counterexample-guided search approach employed in the genetic programming algorithm. Describe how the algorithm utilizes counterexamples resulting from model verification to refine the search process, thereby effectively guiding the exploration towards solutions that better satisfy the specified constraints.

Preedanani et al. [3] proposed new IQA method based on image gradient which is sensitive to the changed detail in

images. This metric computed the similarity of gradient direction and also apply gradient magnitude information to weight these similarity values in pooling process.

Bansal et al. [4] focuses on blur detection and noise estimates. It makes use of a technique for estimating Gaussian noise and edge and sharpness analysis via the Laplacian operator for blur detection. Experimental results and comparative analysis corroborate the method, which only needs one adaptive parameter and works well with various image kinds and noise levels.

Mahmood [5] introduced GP-RDP, employing genetic programming for automatic region detection in image classification. It outperforms other methods on challenging datasets while offering interpretability through evolved programs analysis.

Bakurov et al. [6] propose a novel approach for formulating SSIM-like image quality measures via genetic programming. They highlight the effectiveness of hand-crafted SSIM and explore genetic optimization to enhance performance, showing superior correlation with human mean opinion scores.

Fan et al.[7] proposed a region adaptive image classification technique leveraging GP to automatically extract features from diverse descriptors. Their approach demonstrated superior performance compared to existing methods, indicating its versatility and interpretability across multiple datasets.

Roosbahani et al.[8] introduced an innovative method for face detection from blurred images using convolutional neural network. Their study outperforms existing techniques, tackling issues like noise and blur, with implications in surveillance, crowd identification, and image alignment across various wavelengths.

1. III. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of the project is to develop a robust system for detecting blur and obfuscation in images. This entails leveraging genetic programming techniques to create a reliable classification model capable of accurately identifying instances of blur and obfuscation within the image data. The various steps for the detection includes:

A. Data Collection

The image blur and obfuscation detection dataset emphasizes how important data collection is to machine learning, particularly in specialized fields. There are several categories for sharp and blurry images, and there are plenty of samples in each for testing and training. Since each image represents either blur or sharpness, they serve as an essential training set for models that are supposed to be able to distinguish between the two classes.

Fig. 1. Sample dataset images

1. B. Data Processing

The image data undergoes preprocessing which includes Laplacian variance and edge intensity, using Opencv library. These two functions are pivotal for feature extraction in image processing tasks. The first function calculates the variance of the Laplacian operator applied to the grayscale representation of an image, providing insights into its sharpness and level of detail. Meanwhile, the second function employs the Canny edge detection technique to compute the average intensity of edges present in the grayscale image, offering information about the overall edge content and complexity. Together, these functions enable the extraction of key features from images, facilitating further analysis and categorization.

C. Model training

In training, the GP model's symbolic expressions are iteratively refined to reflect the subtle link between input image attributes and output labels that indicate sharpness or blur. The model refines its expressions across several generations in order to improve fit with the training set. After training is complete, the model uses the symbolic expressions it has learnt to analyze extracted features from new photos and forecast whether or not they will be blurry. This predictive power is a useful tool for evaluating image quality, directing judgment calls, and providing context for the next stages of image processing workflows. The GP model enhances image analysis and interpretation by effectively and precisely identifying picture blur through the utilization of the knowledge obtained from its trained expressions.

IV.IMPLEMENTATION

A. Import necessary libraries such as gplearn-genetic, numpy, scikit-learn, matplotlib to facilitate data processing, model training, evaluation and visualization.

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
from gplearn.genetic import SymbolicRegressor
import os
import joblib
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

Fig. 2. Importing libraries

B. After importing the required libraries, the dataset must be loaded. The dataset sourced from Kaggle contains

images categorized into two classes: Blur images and sharp images.

```

2 usages
def extract_laplacian_variance(image):
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    laplacian = cv2.Laplacian(gray, cv2.CV_64F)
    return np.var(laplacian)

2 usages
def extract_edge_intensity(image):
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    edges = cv2.Canny(gray, 50, 150)
    return np.mean(edges)
    
```

Fig. 3. Function for Feature Extraction

- C. In image preprocessing, OpenCV's cv2.imread function loads images, cv2.cvtColor function converts BGR to grayscale, cv2.Laplacian function applies edge detection, and cv2.Canny refines edges using the Canny algorithm. These functions collectively prepare images for analysis by highlighting features and enhancing their representation for subsequent tasks.

```

2 usages
def get_image_paths(folder_path):
    image_paths = []
    for filename in os.listdir(folder_path):
        if filename.endswith(".jpg") or filename.endswith(".jpeg") or filename.endswith(".png"):
            image_paths.append(os.path.join(folder_path, filename))
    return image_paths

gp_model = SymbolicRegressor(population_size=100, generations=50)
    
```

Fig. 4. Setting up the GP Model

- D. The gp_model, on the other hand, is an example of a symbolic regression model that was created through the use of a GP algorithm. This model is configured to evolve over 50 generations, starting with a population of 100. This approach, along with other symbolic regression models, is intended to automatically find mathematical expressions that best suit the connections between goal values and input variables. They perform exceptionally well in activities that require them to identify a symbolic representation of intricate data patterns.

```

def train_gp_model(X_train, y_train):
    gp_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    joblib.dump(gp_model, filename='gp_model.pkl')
    print("GP model saved.")

1 usage
def predict_image_blur(image_path):
    image = cv2.imread(image_path)
    features = [extract_laplacian_variance(image), extract_edge_intensity(image)]
    prediction = gp_model.predict(np.array(features).reshape(1, -1))

    if prediction == 1:
        print("The image is blurred.")
        return True # Return True if image is blurred
    else:
        print("The image is sharp.")
        return False # Return False if image is sharp
    
```

Fig. 5. Model is saved and used for blur detection

V.RESULT

The study describes an automated system that combines machine learning and image processing methods to discern between clear and blurry photos. To create a dataset, features related to edge intensity and Laplacian variance are first taken out of the pictures. Then, using this dataset, a GP model is trained to distinguish between clear and blurry photos. The model's ability to distinguish between the two groups shows encouraging accuracy. After training successfully, the system is used to forecast a fresh image's sharpness, giving important information for later processing stages. The technique demonstrates the promise of such hybrid approaches in image analysis tasks by combining GP algorithms with computer vision.

Upload Profile Image

Choose Image:

image.jpg

Fig 6. Interface for uploading image and checking blur

Result

Fig. 7. Interface for showing results`

A. Analysis

For the GP model to be useful in practice, its performance is essential. It is necessary to evaluate how well it classifies photos, particularly when image sharpness plays a significant role. Metrics like recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score give a clear picture of the model's strengths and weaknesses. Fig 3. represents the performance metrics of the model.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support	
	0.0	0.67	1.00	0.80	4
	1.0	1.00	0.50	0.67	4
accuracy			0.75	8	
macro avg	0.83	0.75	0.73	8	
weighted avg	0.83	0.75	0.73	8	

Fig. 8. Performance metrics of the model

The confusion matrix is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a classification model on a set of test data for which the true values are known. Fig. 9. represents the confusion matrix of the model. Each row of the matrix represents the instances in an actual class, while each column represents the instances in a predicted class.

Fig. 9. Confusion matrix for predicting blur

B. Comparison

A region adaptive image classification method based on GP was presented in a paper by Qinglan et al.[7]. This technique uses various image descriptors in different areas of a picture to automatically extract informative image features. With a 70% accuracy rate on many datasets, the authors' innovative flexible GP program structure with a new function set and terminal set produced competitive or better results than baseline approaches. On the other hand, the approach put forward in this work uses genetic programming to tackle the crucial problem of identifying blur and obfuscation in images. Using a hand-picked dataset created just for this use, this proposed strategy outperformed conventional approaches with an accuracy of 75%. Applications like security and image processing.

VI.CONCLUSION

The objective of this work is to classify images using a novel approach that leverages GP to distinguish between clear and blurry images. The proposed model utilizes edge intensity and Laplacian variance for feature extraction.

The paper suggests further development, proposing that integrating Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) into the framework could potentially offer a more reliable solution for image analysis and other applications, enhancing its functionality and cross-domain adaptability. Future research may explore the synergy of CNNs and GP to improve feature extraction performance and increase flexibility. Additionally, training with more diverse large datasets could be pursued to further enhance accuracy and robustness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Bi, M. Zhang and B. Xue, (2022), " Using a small number of training instances in genetic programming for face image classification", International Conference on Image and Vision Computing New Zealand (IVCNZ), Christchurch, New Zealand, Vol.1(1). pp. 488-504.
- [2] I. Bładek and K. Krawiec, (2023),"Counterexample-Driven Genetic Programming for Symbolic Regression With Formal Constraints," in IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, Vol. 27(5), pp. 1327-1339.
- [3] W. Preedan, T. Kondo, P. Bunnun and I. Kumazawa(2018), "Image quality assessment for medical images based on gradient information," 5th International Conference on Business and Industrial Research (ICBIR), Bangkok, Thailand Vol.1(2)pp. 189-194.
- [4] R. Bansal, G. Raj and T. Choudhury(2016), "Blur image detection using Laplacian operator and Open-CV," International Conference System Modeling & Advancement in Research Trends (SMART), Moradabad, India, Vol(2)1 pp. 63-67.
- [5] MuhammadTariq Mahmood(2023)"Defocus Blur Segmentation Using Genetic Programming and Adaptive Threshold", (2021), Korea University of Technology and Education, Cheonan, 31253, Byeongcheon-myeon, Korea, CMC, 2022, Vol.70(3),pp 4869.
- [6] I. Bakurov, M. Buzzelli, R. Schettini, M. Castelli and L. Vanneschi(2023),"Full-Reference Image Quality Expression via Genetic Programming," in IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, Vol.32(3), pp. 1458-1473.
- [7] Qinglan Fan, B. Xue and M. Zhang(2020), "A Region Adaptive Image Classification Approach Using Genetic Programming," 2020 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC), Glasgow, UK, Vol.1(1) pp. 1-8.
- [8] K. M. Roozbahani and H. S. Zadeh(2022),"Face Detection from Blurred Images based on Convolutional Neural Networks," 2022 International Conference on Machine Vision and Image Processing (MVIP), Ahvaz, Iran, Islamic Republic of Iran, Vol. 1(1) pp. 1-10.